

GENDER ROLE DIFFERENCES IN HUMORISTIC STYLE

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Scholars and practitioners have argued that humor is a valuable workplace behavior and an important tool for managers. Humor can be defined as a form of communication in which a “humorist” intentionally incorporates humorous incongruities in messages to an audience. The most common form of workplace humor is interpersonal humor, or humor that is directed or targeted toward someone else. Interpersonal humor styles are distinguished as affiliative or aggressive. Affiliative humor is defined as positive interpersonal humor “used to enhance one’s relationships with others in a way that is relatively benign and self-accepting,” while aggressive humor is negative and “used to enhance the self ... at the expense and detriment to one’s relationship with others” Affiliative humor is associated with performance, job satisfaction and cohesiveness, while aggressive humor tends to have negative effects on outcomes. Recently, researchers began examining whether contextual factors influence the impact of workplace humor. For example, researchers have explored how characteristics of the humorist, such as gender, influence humor use and audience responses to humor. For instance, Evans et found that when men use Humor use and social acceptance .

The current issue and full text archive of this journal is available on Emerald Insight at: humor, it is more functional and less disruptive than when women use humor. They also found that female humorists are rated as having lower perceived status than females who do not engage in humor, while male humorists are rated as having higher perceived status than those who do not use humor. However, other

research has shown that when using positive humor, female managers were rated higher than their male counterparts on relationship behavior and leader effectiveness. These divergent findings indicate that additional research is needed to unpack how humorist gender influences humorist perceptions. In this paper, we integrate social role theory with expectancy violation theory to explore the notion that society expects men and women to use humor differently, and that violations of expectations can influence perceptions of those humorists. These two theories are particularly informative for this research because social role theory provides an explanation for why behavioral expectations differ for men and women humorists while EVT provides an explanation for why some humorists' violations of behavioral expectations result in more positive evaluations, while others result in more negative evaluations. We also extend prior research by considering how differences in a humorist's formal organizational status influence behavioral expectations and perceptions of the humorist, whereas previous research has primarily focused on how manager humor impacts employees or on a humorist's perceived status as a dependent variable.

We present two studies examining whether behavioral expectations differentially impact perceptions of women who use humor at work relative to men and whether formal status is an important contextual condition impacting those perceptions. Study 1 explored predictions concerning the use of aggressive humor. In Study 2, we shifted our focus to examine predictions concerning the use of affiliative humor. Social roles Research on gender differences has shown that men and women generally exhibit different behaviors in social settings According to social role theory, these behavioral differences stem from men's and women's divergent social roles. Male gender roles are associated with agentic attributes such as being assertive, independent and controlling. Conversely, female gender roles are associated with communal attributes such as caring for others and being sensitive, selfless and emotionally expressive Because of their masculine and feminine leanings, agentic and communal attributes dictate normative expectations

for how men and women should behave and these attributes have been found to influence behaviors and outcomes such as men's and women's career pursuits and occupational success. Unfortunately, gender-stereotyped beliefs often disadvantage professional women, particularly in terms of leadership emergence. According to male gender prescriptions, it is socially acceptable for men to act agentically; however, men are also allowed to exhibit communal behaviors, such as chivalry and courteousness.

In the current study, we provide an explanation for gender-specific responses to humor in advertising. We focus on conversational humor, which is the most frequent cause of laughter in natural social interactions, as opposed to unintentional humor. We draw on evolutionary psychology and suggest that gender-specific differences in responses to conversational humor depend on the use of different humor types and their function as an indicator of mental fitness and a signal of good genes.

More specifically, we argue that ads containing canned humor are a bad signal, while spontaneous humor that occurs more naturally during the course of a social interaction increases women's reactions toward it. The study contributes to advertising research by suggesting that differences in humor types can explain gender-specific responses to conversational humor in advertising. It further substantiates the application and usefulness of an evolutionary explanation for humor effects in advertising, an explanation that was largely neglected in prior research on humor in advertising. The paper further contributes to advertising practice in that the results aid in designing advertisements that address the humor preferences of the targeted gender.

To test the hypotheses and answer the research question, we conducted three experimental studies. Study 1 addresses the research question and the first and second hypotheses using a three-factor between-subject experimental design with humor type and source of humor (female vs. male) as manipulated factors, and gender (female vs. male) as a measured factor. Study replicates the results of study

1 related to the male source and introduces interest in pursuing romantic activities as another moderator and potential boundary condition for the hypothesized interactive effect of gender and humor type on perceived humorousness. Study 2 follows a three-factor between-subject experimental design with humor type (spontaneous vs. canned) as a manipulated factor, and gender (female vs. male) and interest in pursuing romantic activities as measured factors. To provide further support for our hypotheses, study 3 follows and replicates the experimental design of study 2 with different advertising stimuli. Following prior research, participants' age in the three studies was restricted to 50 years old, because our paper focuses on consumers that can adequately engage in reproductive behaviours.

Future research might explore other advertising elements that can serve as honest or fake signals of mental fitness and good genes and thus influence consumers. For instance, physical beauty is a strong signal from an evolutionary perspective, but can be easily manipulated and faked in advertising. A recent study by Yoon and Lee that adopted evolutionary psychology as a theoretical foundation opens another pathway to future research. The two scholars demonstrated that gender differences in humorous ad processing might be explained by differences in arousal seeking tendencies of the two genders.

References

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